

Active packaging for table grapes: Evaluation of antimicrobial performances of packaging for shelf life of the grapes under thermal stress

Giuliana Gorrasi^{a,*}, Valeria Bugatti^{a,b}, Luigi Vertuccio^a, Vittoria Vittoria^{a,b}, Bernardo Pace^c, Maria Cefola^c, Laura Quintieri^d, Paola Bernardo^e, Gabriele Clarizia^e

^a Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Salerno, via Giovanni Paolo II, 132, 84084 Fisciano, SA, Italy

^b Nice Filler s.r.l., via Loggia dei Pisani, 25, 80133 Napoli, Italy

^c Institute of Sciences of Food Production, National Research Council of Italy (CNR), c/o CS-DAT, Via Michele Protano, 71121 Foggia, Italy

^d Institute of Sciences of Food Production, National Research Council of Italy (CNR), Via G. Amendola, 122/O, 70126 Bari, Italy

^e Institute on Membrane Technology (ITM-CNR), c/o University of Calabria, via P. Bucci 17/C, 87036 Rende, CS, Italy

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Layered double hydroxides
Active coating
Antimicrobial
Table grapes

ABSTRACT

The paper reports the formulation of an active packaging based on PET coated with a Layered Double Hydroxide (LDH) hosting 2-acetoxybenzoic anion (salicylate) as antimicrobial molecule. The release of the molecule anchored to the LDH, compared to the molecule free dispersed into the coating, appeared much slower. Permeability of carbon dioxide and oxygen through the packaging at different temperatures was evaluated, as well as the capability of the active material to inhibit *Pseudomonas*, *Listeria* and *Lactobacillus*. Table grape was stored in thermal stress conditions (i.e. 10 °C) into the active packaging and the total mesophilic aerobic count and yeasts and moulds population was evaluated up to 14 days of storage. The experimental results were used for a theoretical prediction of shelf life of the packed grapes and compared with the same fruit packed into untreated material. Global and specific migration of salicylic acid from the active packaging demonstrated, in compliance with the migration limits of the EU regulation, the suitability of the considered material for food contact.

1. Introduction

In recent years, the food packaging materials based on polymers are in continuous evolution, in response to the increasingly complex needs of the markets, of the distribution times and conditions and of consumers' safety. Therefore, packaging systems are becoming increasingly sophisticated thanks to the rapid evolution of science and technology in producing new materials. The fast development of nanotechnologies is accelerating the innovation in food packaging field and several applications of nanomaterials in packaging and food safety have been studied and developed. They include, for instance, composites based on polymer and active nano-fillers as high barrier packaging materials, reservoirs of antimicrobial agents, nanosensors for the detection of food contaminants or monitoring the packaging conditions integrity (Bugatti, Vertuccio, Zuppari, Vittoria, & Gorrasi, 2019; Duncan, 2011; Gan & Chow, 2018; Pucciariello et al., 2004; Sorrentino, Gorrasi, & Vittoria, 2007; Souza & Fernando, 2016). Active packaging systems are developed with the goal of extending shelf life for foods and increasing the period of time in which the food is of high quality. The controlled release of antimicrobials from packaging materials represents an

important innovation in active packaging. Antimicrobials incorporated in packaging materials could extend shelf life by preventing bacterial growth and spoilage. This system could potentially increase the stability and specificity of preservation and reduce the amount of chemicals needed in foods. It has been demonstrated that the use of nanostructures can achieve levels of functionalities in some cases very difficult to reach using bulk materials. The use of hybrid inorganic-organic materials is increasing considerably, in fact manipulating on nanometer scale the matter it is possible to design advanced materials with specific structure and functionalities. Among the inorganic fillers that can modify the polymers' properties and functionalities, Layered Double Hydroxides (LDH) are very attractive and versatile (Costantino, Marmottini, Nocchetti, & Vivani, 1998; Costantino, Nocchetti, Gorrasi, & Tammaro, 2011). They are composed of positively charged brucite-like layers of divalent and trivalent metal hydroxides in which the excess of positive charge is compensated by anions and water molecules between the interstitial position. They can be represented by the general formula:

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: ggorrasi@unisa.it (G. Gorrasi).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fpsl.2020.100545>

Received 18 March 2020; Received in revised form 2 July 2020; Accepted 6 July 2020

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where M(II) = Mg, Ni, Co, Cu, Zn, Mn; M(III) = Al, Fe, Cr, V; $A^{n-} = CO_3^{2-}, Cl^-, SO_4^{2-}, etc.$, and $x = 0.1 - 0.35$. High performance thermoplastic polymers generally need high temperatures and shear forces during the processing of incorporation of fillers and nano-fillers, such conditions can cause the degradation of the active molecules that are thermolabile. It has been demonstrated that LDH layers can protect the intercalated molecules which maintain their activity even after drastic processing conditions (Sorrentino et al., 2007). They are biocompatible and can be produced with simple procedures and high level of purity, and have been widely proposed in drug delivery and as carrier of antimicrobials as hybrid nanofillers into polymers (Gorrasi & Sorrentino, 2015; Velasco, Ardanuy, & Antunes, 2012). Table grape (*Vitis Vinifera* L.) is a nonclimateric fruit with serious problems during postharvest handling, storage and marketing. It loses quality accompanied to weight loss, color changes and softening (Carvajal-Millán et al., 2001; Crisosto, Garner, & Crisosto, 2002). All these detrimental effects lead to quality losses and high occurrence of decay during prolonged storage (Palou, Crisosto, Smilanick, Adaskaveg, & Zoffoli, 2002; Valverde et al., 2005). Disease in table grape is caused by different microorganisms: acetic acid bacteria (*Gluconobacter* spp., *Acetobacter* spp.), yeasts (*Zygosaccharomyces* spp.) and moulds (*Botrytis cinerea*); these latter induce uncontrolled infections that allow the development of aerial mycelium spreading rapidly to adjacent berries with severe economic repercussions. Several methods have been used to preserve table grape, the most common is SO_2 , but sulfite residue is a problem associated with SO_2 fumigations. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) established the maximum tolerance to sulfite residues at $10 \mu L/L$, while the European Union forbidden the use of SO_2 (EU Directive 95/2/CE). In this optic, the pesticide usage associated to the development of fungicide-resistant strains and the public's concern for the environmental pollution and the human health are stimulating the research toward new strategies as alternative means for controlling postharvest decay. It is, then, fundamental to find alternative and safe active systems able to preserve fresh fruits, like table grapes, and to extend their shelf life with the same performances of SO_2 . In this paper, we report the preparation of an active packaging based on a PET tray with an active coating composed of a food grade resin filled with LDH hosting salicylate anion as antimicrobial agent (listed in EC-Directive 10/2011/EC of 14 January 2011). Structure and thermal properties of the filler was evaluated. Barrier properties against O_2 and CO_2 at different temperatures and *in vitro* inhibition of bacteria spoilage were analyzed. Table grapes were packaged at $10^\circ C$ and it was evaluated the total mesophilic aerobic count, yeasts and moulds population, and compared to the same table grapes packaged in not treated packaging. The shelf life of the packaged grapes was estimated on the basis of the evolution of yeasts and moulds during the 14 days of storage, using the Gompertz's model.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

Poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) (B.PET TRA S2 F740 S350, 2157400350) used for the trays, was supplied by Aristeia spa, Salerno (Italy) in laminate form $350 \mu m$ thick. These laminates were then processed in trays. The active filler, having the trade name of A6B6® and based on a LDH intercalated with antimicrobial salicylate anion (listed in EC-Directive 10/2011), was produced by Nicefiller Ltd, a startup of the University of Salerno (Italy). The synthesis was conducted accordingly to a previously reported procedure (Frunza, Lisa, Popa, Miron, & Nistor, 2008). The resin used for coating was a water-based paint normally used for food packaging (Inx 1-7801-7000, solid content $42 \pm 2\%$, viscosity 20 s at $20^\circ C$) purchased from Inx srl (Lodi, Italy). Its constituents are in accordance with the EC-Directive 2002/72 including amendments. The resin and the active filler (A6B6®) at 5 wt% were mixed using high energy ball milling at room temperature, for

30 min at 450 rpm and coated on PET (sample named PET/Active) by using an automatic coater. The composite filler weight was $12 \pm 0.5 g/m^2$ on dry resin. The laminates after the coating phase were thermofomed to obtain the active trays. A sample of PET with the active molecule simply mixed into the coating was prepared in the same described experimental conditions.

2.2. Methods

X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were taken in reflection mode with an automatic Bruker diffractometer D8, using nickel-filtered Cu K α radiation ($K\alpha = 1.54050 \text{ \AA}$) and operating at 40 kV and 40 mA, with a step scan of 0.05° of 2θ and 3 s of counting time.

Gas permeation rates were measured on circular samples with an effective area of 34.2 cm^2 that were cut from the top of the trays. Their thickness was obtained as the average of multiple measurements taken with a digital micrometer (Series 293, Mitutoyo, Milano, Italy). The fixed volume/pressure increase instrument (Elektro & Elektronik Service Reuter, Geesthacht, Germany) and the testing procedure are described elsewhere (Clarizia, Bernardo, Gorrasi, Zampino, & Carroccio, 2018). The tests were conducted at a feed pressure of 1 bar in the temperature range $15 - 55^\circ C$ with single gases (O_2 and CO_2 from SAPIO, Milano, Italy). Before each test, the samples were evacuated with a series of membrane and turbo molecular pumps to remove humidity or other dissolved species. In particular, owing to the combination of high sample thickness and low permeability, the membrane evacuation time was about two weeks at the lowest temperature. According to the 'solution-diffusion' mechanism, that describes the gas transport through dense polymeric films (Wijmans & Baker, 1995), the gas permeability (P) can be expressed as product of diffusion (D) and solubility (S) coefficients, $P = DS$. The gas permeability (P) was obtained from the slope of the pressure vs. time curve at steady-state conditions. According to the time-lag method, the diffusion coefficient (D) was calculated combining the membrane thickness (l) and the gas time-lag (θ) that is the intercept on the time axis of the linear portion of the pressure curve. The solubility coefficient was indirectly obtained from permeability and diffusion ($S = P/D$). The ideal selectivity for the two gases was obtained as the ratio of their individual permeability values. This parameter can be decoupled in solubility- and diffusion-selectivity terms.

The release kinetics of salicylate were followed using a Shimadzu UV-2401 PC spectrometer. The tests were performed using 4 cm^2 rectangular specimens placed into 25 mL physiological solution and stirred at 100 rpm in an orbital shaker (VDRL MOD. 711+, Asal). The release medium was withdrawn at fixed time intervals and replenished with fresh medium. The considered band was 230 nm.

The *in-vitro* effect of inhibition against *Pseudomonas*, *Listeria* and *Lactobacillus* by the treated PET trays was analyzed following the directive ISO 22196:2011: such method evaluates the antibacterial activity of treated plastics, surfaces and other non-porous materials.

Overall migration tests were performed on the PET trays treated with A6B6® filler samples according to the following procedure: lamina specimens having 1 dm^2 of surface area ($10 \text{ cm} \times 10 \text{ cm}$, 0.10 mm thickness) were put into contact with 100 mL of simulant (preconditioned at $40^\circ C$) in a borosilicate glass tube closed with a screw cap internally layered with Teflon®. The obtained surface/volume ratio was $10 \text{ dm}^2/L$. Migration tests after contact for 10 days at $40^\circ C$ were performed using C (ethanol at 20 %) and D1 (ethanol at 50 %) as simulants. The overall migration test was performed on different aliquots from the same contact sample. The overall migration results were calculated by using $6 \text{ dm}^2/\text{kg}$ food ($6 \text{ dm}^2/L$ simulant) as conventional EU surface/volume ratio. A known aliquot of the simulant from the contact solution was transferred into a weighted quartz capsule and evaporated to dryness until constant weight. From the differences between the weights, the overall migration was derived in accordance to EN 1186 Migration Testing for Food Contact Materials. The data were averaged on five samples.

Microbiological tests were carried out on table grapes (*Vitis vinifera* L., cv Egnathia) provided by an experimental farm conducted by Research Centre for Viticulture and Enology (CREA, Turi, Italy). Bunches were harvested at the maturity stage (total soluble solid content of about 20° Brix) and transported within two hours from harvest to the Postharvest laboratory. Samples were selected on the basis of the absence of defects, divided in small pieces (berries with rachis of about 450 g) and randomly closed in PET trays (165 × 135 × 45 mm) with active filler (AF) or without (Control, C). A total of 24 trays (3 replicates × 2 packages × 4 storage times after 4, 7, 11 and 14 days) were stored at 10 °C. Just after harvest (fresh sample) and at each storage time, samples were analysed for the incidence of visible mould on berries and microbiological analysis measuring the lactic acid bacteria, total mesophilic aerobic bacteria, and moulds and yeasts.

The mould incidence on berries was evaluated counting berries with visible mould on each bunch for each replicate in C or AF packages. It was expressed as percentage of infected berries respect to total one.

For microbiology analysis, fifty grams of berries from each packaging (C or AF) were rinsed, in triplicate, in 450 mL of 0.1 % peptone water with 0.02 % Tween 20 by orbital shaking (CERTOMAT® HK, Sartorius AG, Göttingen, Germany) in a flask at 170 strokes/min for 30 min (Garofalo, Tristezza, Grieco, Spano, & Capozzi, 2016). Then, each sample was decimally diluted in 0.1 % (w/v) sterile saline solution (0.9 % NaCl) before plating on the selective media. In particular, yeasts and moulds were detected on Dichloran Rose Bengal Chloramphenicol Agar (DRBC, Biolife Italiana srl, Milan, Italy) and incubated at 25 °C for 3–5 days (ISO 21527-1, 2008); lactic acid bacteria population (LABs) were counted on De Man, Rogosa and Sharpe agar (MRS, Biolife Italiana srl, Milan, Italy) supplemented with 100 mg/L of cycloheximide after incubation at 30 °C for 48 h (ISO-15214, 1998); total mesophilic aerobic counts (TBC) were enumerated on Plate Count Agar (PCA, Biolife Italiana srl, Milan, Italy) supplemented with 100 mg/L of cycloheximide after incubation at 30 °C for 24 h (ISO 4833, 2003).

A two-way ANOVA test was performed using SPSS 20.0 (IBM, Armonk, NY, USA) to examine the effects of storage and packaging (C or AF) on the incidence of visible moulds and on the microbial load of different microbial groups after assessing variance homogeneity with Levene's test ($P < 0.05$). Multiple comparisons within the same microbial group were made by Fisher's least significant difference (LSD, C.I. > = 95 %); wherever required, a two-tail independent *t*-test ($\alpha = 0.05$) was also performed.

3. Results and discussion

Fig. 1 reports the XRD of the pristine LDH in nitrate form (Fig. 1(A)) with the basal spacing at 10.2° of 2 θ ($d = 8.6 \text{ \AA}$). The basal spacing increased from 8.6 Å to 16.3 Å, corresponding to 2 $\theta \cong 6.02^\circ$ (Fig. 1(B)),

Fig. 1. XRD of pristine LDH in nitrate form (A) and LDH-salicylate anion (B).

Fig. 2. Release kinetics of the active molecule anchored to the active filler in PET (■) and of the active molecule simply dispersed into PET (●).

and this is a clear probe of the successful intercalation of the salicylate anion into LDH layers.

The possibility to obtain a polymer/active filler system with slow and controlled release is crucial in the active packaging, in order to increase the shelf life of the packed food. When an active molecule is simply dispersed into a polymer matrix its release is driven by a fast diffusion. On the other hand, if it is fixed with a chemical bond, the release can be dependent on several factors, such as medium of interaction of the whole system that influences the ionic exchange reaction between the intercalated molecular anions and the counter-ions present into the release medium. Fig. 2 reports the release kinetics from the PET trays of the active molecule anchored to the active filler and the salicylate simply dispersed into the polymer matrix. A first stage, corresponding to the release from the surface, is followed by a second stage that corresponds to the de-intercalation of the salicylate bonded to the LDH lamellae. It is evident that, at any release time, the molecule from the active packaging shows a slower release. It is worth to note that, in the considered contact time (30 days), the active molecule anchored to the filler was not completely released.

The data obtained from the gas permeation tests on the trays are summarized in Table 1.

CO₂ was the most permeable gas in both tray types. A detailed analysis of the two contributions to permeability (namely, diffusion and solubility) allows to recognize that the CO₂ molecules has a higher solubility than O₂ and this contribute is predominant in determining its higher permeability.

The PET/Active trays displayed a partial change in the transport properties with respect to those not treated. In particular, they presented a faster CO₂ transport, with a 65 % increase in permeability. On the contrary, the O₂ permeability was almost unchanged. Consequently, the CO₂/O₂ ideal selectivity increased in the PET/Active trays (+68 %).

The apparent diffusion coefficient for CO₂ was unaffected in the PET/Active trays, while it was reduced for the O₂. On the other hand, the presence of the inorganic fillers in the PET/Active trays lead to an

Table 1
Gas transport properties evaluated in the trays at 25 °C.

Material		O ₂	CO ₂	CO ₂ /O ₂
PET	Permeability (Barrer)	0.099	0.26	2.6
	D ($10^{-8} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$)	0.43	0.11	0.26
	S ($\text{cm}^3(\text{STP}) \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ bar}^{-1}$)	0.17	1.7	10
PET/Active	Permeability (Barrer)	0.097	0.43	4.4
	D ($10^{-8} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$)	0.36	0.11	0.31
	S ($\text{cm}^3(\text{STP}) \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ bar}^{-1}$)	0.20	2.9	15

1 Barrer = $10^{-10} \text{ cm}^3 (\text{STP}) \text{ cm cm}^{-2} \text{ cmHg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Fig. 3. Permeability logarithm versus reciprocal of absolute temperature plot, for CO₂ and O₂ measured in the PET/Active trays.

increased solubility for both gases, particularly for CO₂. Accordingly, it was observed increment in the CO₂/O₂ ideal selectivity, and this contribution was due mainly to the solubility parameter. The gas permeation tests demonstrated that the active coating combined to the thermoforming process was able to keep unchanged the barrier properties for the O₂ transport, but at the same time, the CO₂ transport through the trays was enhanced. These features favor the CO₂ outflow from the packaged product. The calculation of activation energy for the permeation process of both gas species (CO₂ and O₂) allows to analyze the response of material to the gas transport in dependence of temperature change. An Arrhenius trend was observed (Fig. 3), that is, there is a linear relationship between the gas permeability logarithm and the reciprocal of absolute temperature (T). Thus, P can be expressed as:

$$P = P_0 \exp(-E_p/RT) \quad (1)$$

where P_0 is the pre-exponential factor of permeation, E_p is the activation energy for permeation, and R is the gas constant.

As expected from the order of gas permeability and endothermicity of the sorption process, E_p for CO₂ was lower than for O₂ (25.2 and 35.5 kJ mol⁻¹), respectively. Additionally, as the temperature increased, CO₂/O₂ selectivity decreased. It results since the diffusion coefficient tends to increase with temperature as consequence of the enhanced mobility of gas molecules as well as the segmental chain mobility in polymer, whereas the solubility coefficient decreases. Therefore, the permeability of CO₂, depending on solubility term more

markedly than O₂, was less influenced on temperature with respect to O₂.

The evaluation of the bacterial inhibition from the treated PET trays was carried out using *Pseudomonas*, *Listeria* and *Lactobacillus* bacterial strains. The test microorganisms were prepared by growth in a liquid culture medium. The suspension of the test microorganisms was standardized by dilution in a nutritive broth, then control and test surfaces were inoculated with microorganisms, in triplicate, and the microbial inoculum was covered with a sterile film. In order to provide a comparison, all microbiological assay runs were performed with the necessary parallel controls for the whole time of the experiments. Microbial concentrations were determined at "time zero" by elution followed by dilution and plating. A control was run to verify that the neutralization/elution method effectively neutralized the antimicrobial agents in the antimicrobial surface being tested. Inoculated, covered control and antimicrobial test surfaces were allowed to incubate in a humid environment for 24 h and microbial concentrations were determined. The reduction of microorganisms relative to initial concentrations and the control surface was calculated. By including the proper controls and being able to make these reduction calculations, such assay allowed to evaluate whether the treated PET tray is bacteriostatic, having the ability to inhibit the growth of microorganisms. Table 2 reports the experimental conditions and results. For all considered strains, a significant antibacterial activity from the studied active packaging is evident.

The incidence of visible mould on berries was significantly affected only by packaging ($p < 0.001$); in detail, a mean incidence of 2.8 % was recorded on C, while 0.9 % was the value calculated for AF packages on the whole storage. Thus, based on this visual evaluation, the presence of the AF resulted able to limit the mould development on berries. As for microbial evaluation, there was a statistically significant interaction between factors level on load within each microbial group, ($p < 0.00001$). As shown in Fig. 4(A), table grapes registered a low initial value of LABs load that reached 4.59 (± 0.13) log CFU/g for fruits packed in C trays at the 7th day of storage. These results were in accordance with Barata, Malfeito-Ferreira, and Loureiro (2012) which found low populations of LAB on both healthy and sour rotten grapes. Starting from the 4th day of storage, a significantly lower value (3.5 log CFU/g, on average; $P < 0.05$) was instead registered in PET/Active trays in comparison to control sample (4.15 log CFU/g, on average) (Fig. 4(A)). As regard total mesophilic aerobic count (TBC), simple main effects analysis showed that time of incubation did not affect microbial load for both samples ($P > 0.05$); however, TBC values on samples from AF packaging were significantly lower ($P < 0.05$; Student's t -test) than those from C trays throughout the entire period of incubation (Fig. 4(B)). The significant antimicrobial effect of salicylate anion released from PET/Active tray was also registered for yeasts and moulds population (Fig. 4(C); $P < 0.001$); this latter, primarily responsible for microbial spoilage activity on grapes (Pinto, Caputo, Quintieri, de

Table 2
Inhibition of *Pseudomonas*, *Listeria* and *Lactobacillus* from the PET/Active trays.

Bacterial strain	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> ATCC 15442	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> ATCC13932	<i>Lactobacillus sakei</i> - ATCC 15521
Sample size	50 × 50 (mm × mm)	50 × 50 (mm × mm)	50 × 50 (mm × mm)
Sample thickness	1.0 mm	2.0 mm	0.1 mm
Inoculum volume	0.4 mL	0.4 mL	0.4 mL
U ₀ : Number of bacteria available in the inoculum	410.000	380.000	35.000
U _t : Count of bacteria recovered from non-treated samples after 24 h from inoculation	5.3 (log)	4.8 (log)	2.5 (log)
A _t : Count of bacteria recovered from treated samples after 24 h from inoculation	n.d. ^a	3.0 (log)	0.8 (log)
Antibacterial activity	> 5.3	1.7	1.6
R = (U _t -U ₀)-(A _t -U ₀) (ISO 22196:2011)			

^a Not detectable.

Fig. 4. Bacterial counts (expressed as log CFU/g) of A) lactic acid bacteria, LABs, B) total mesophilic aerobic bacteria, TBC, and C) mould and yeast, M/Y in table grapes packed in PET (C) or PET/Active (AF) trays during incubation at 10 °C for 14 days. Values represent the average ± the standard deviation (n = 3). Differences among ΔlogCFU/g values higher than 0.41 (A) and 0.64 (C) (Fisher's LSD) separate significantly different means. B) Asterisks indicate statistically significance differences (Student's test, α < 0.05 assuming equal variances).

Fig. 5. Time course during storage of grapes at 10 °C in PET (control) and PET active film. The curves are the best fit using Eq. (2).

Table 3

Model parameters referred to Eq. (2): the increase in log CFU/g between time = 0 and the maximum population density achieved at the stationary phase (A), the maximal specific growth rate (μ_{max}) and the lag time (λ).

Sample	A [log (CFU/g)]	μ_{max} [log (CFU/g)/d]	lag time (λ) [d]
Control	1.658 [1.640 1.676]	0.451 [0.439 0.462]	1.921 [1.837 2.006]
Active film	0.913 [0.902 0.923]	0.486 [0.464 0.507]	3.770 [3.730 3.809]

Candia, & Baruzzi, 2017; Sanzani, Schena, De Cicco, & Ippolito, 2012), showed a reduction of ca. 1.5 log CFU/g after 14 days of storage in PET/Active trays in comparison to C ones. Decay of table grape during storage is mainly due to moulds development, which limits the product marketability favoring waste (Romanazzi, Lichter, Gabler, & Smilanick, 2012). The antimicrobial effect of PET/Active trays is due to the salicylate anion release responsible for changes in cell membrane permeability of several Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, as reported by other authors (Kaduskar, et al., 2017; Bandara, Sankaridurg, Zhu, Hume & Willcox, 2016). To prevent table grape decay in

Table 4
Global migration and specific migration of salicylic acid from the active PET trays.

Simulant	C - ethanol at 20 % (v/v)	D1 - ethanol at 50 % (v/v)	Limits
	Global migration into aqueous food simulant by filling a container UNI EN 1186-1: 2003 + UNI EN 1186-9: 2003	Global migration into aqueous food simulant by filling a container UNI EN 1186-1: 2003 + UNI EN 1186-9: 2003	
Temperature of the test	40 °C	40 °C	
Contact time	10 days	10 days	
Global migration average in the simulant	5.2 (mg/dm ²)	9.0 (mg/dm ²)	10 (mg/dm ²)

postharvest caused by mould development, different antimicrobial agents and physical treatments were found effective; mould contamination is also responsible for mycotoxin production impacting on human health (Romanazzi et al., 2012; Ubeda, Hornedo-Ortega, Cerezo, Garcia-Parrilla, & Troncoso, 2020). However, most of these treatments should be applied to bunches immediately after harvesting and in specific equipments; thus, their antimicrobial effect decline during the next first days of storage. By contrast, the use of the antimicrobial packaging allow to control deterioration of table grapes throughout storage period by preserving shelf life until to the domestic use. In addition to the functionalization of packaging materials with an antimicrobial agent, the use of modified atmosphere (such as 20 % O₂ plus 10 % CO₂) is a further strategy to preserve grape shelf life during its transport and cold storage (Cefola & Pace, 2016). Indeed, table grapes packed in active PET bags and closed in modified atmosphere resulted in an extension of marketability and antioxidant activity over the storage period, also in comparison to the use of SO₂ pads (Cefola, Pace, Bugatti & Vittoria, 2015). In addition, the use of this activated PET bags (Cefola et al., 2015) allowed a release in antioxidants able to control the rachis browning, associated with water loss (Lichter et al., 2011) and oxidation processes (Carvajal-Millán et al., 2001).

The results of microbial growth for yeasts and moulds, and the best fitting of the experimental data are reported in Fig. 5. The fitting of the experimental data has been obtained with a coefficient of determination R² = 0.99, whereas the model parameters, obtained according to the proposed approach in reference (Corbo, Del Nobile, & Sinigaglia, 2006) (95 % confidence intervals), are reported in Table 4.

The generally adopted method (Zwietering, Jongenburger, Roubouts, & van't Riet, 1990) consists in estimating the Gompertz's parameters by fitting the following equation to the experimental data:

$$\log\left(\frac{CFU}{g}\right) = K + A * \exp\left\{-\exp\left[\left(\mu_{max} * 2.7182 \frac{\lambda - t}{A}\right) + 1\right]\right\} \quad (2)$$

where: *K* is the initial level of bacterial count (log CFU/g), *A* is the increase in log CFU/g between start time and the maximum population density achieved at the stationary phase, μ_{max} is the maximal growth rate ($\Delta\log$ (CFU/g)/day), λ is the lag time (days) and *t* is the time (days).

As shown in Table 3, the active system reduces the growth of yeasts and moulds, leading to a decrease of the plateau value of around one order magnitude with respect to the control system.

In the present study, the maximal specific growth rate value (μ_{max}) is essentially the same for both tray types, while the salicylate anion based film inhibits the growth of yeasts and moulds as shown by the increase of the lag time from 1.9 days to 3.8 days. Therefore, the shelf life is extended in the active packaging.

In order to demonstrate that the prepared active packaging is suitable for food contact, we performed overall migration tests on the base of the trays (part in contact with the fruits). Table 4 reports the global migration and specific migration of salicylic acid, evaluated on the active packaging, in different food simulants, accordingly to UNI EN 1186-1:2003 and UNI EN 1186-9: 2003 (ethanol (20 % v/v) and ethanol (50 % v/v)). The experimental results, in compliance with the

migration limits, demonstrate the suitability of the considered material for food contact.

4. Concluding remarks

PET trays with an active coating were prepared and tested for the application in the packaging of table grapes. The Active coating, is based on a food grade acrylic resin filled with Layered Double Hydroxide (LDH) nanofiller hosting antimicrobial 2-acetoxybenzoic anion (salicylate) (listed in EC-Directive 10/2011/EC of 14 January 2011). XRD analysis, revealing an increase of the basal spacing of the pristine clay, proves the successful intercalation of the active molecule inside the LDH galleries. Accordingly, the salicylate has a slower and not complete release from the trays when it is anchored to the LDH fillers compared to a sample in which the molecule is directly dispersed inside the polymer matrix. The active coating, combined to the thermoforming process, maintains the barrier properties for the O₂ transport, enhancing the CO₂ transport rates through the trays. The *in-vitro* bacterial inhibition on the active packaging against *Pseudomonas*, *Listeria* and *Lactobacillus* was analyzed prior to storage of the table grapes, and a significant antibacterial activity was evidenced. Table grape berries were stored in thermal stress conditions (*i.e.* 10 °C) into the active packaging and a significant reduction in total mesophilic aerobic count (TBC) and mould and yeast population, the main responsible for grape spoilage, was observed with respect to control samples. The prediction of shelf life of the fruits stored in the active packaging was elaborated using the Gompertz's equation. Finally, the global migration and specific migration of salicylic acid from the active PET trays in different food simulants, accordingly to UNI EN 1186-1: 2003 and UNI EN 1186-9: 2003 (ethanol (20 % v/v) and ethanol (50 % v/v)), complies with the migration limits. Therefore, the prepared active material is suitable for food contact.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

The project Prin 2017 "MultiFunctional poLYmer cOMposites based on groWn matERials (MIFLOWER)" (grant number: 2017B7MMJ5_001) from the Italian Ministry of Education University and Research Project "High-Performing Advanced Material Platform for Active and Intelligent Food Packaging" is kindly acknowledged.

The project: Cronogard™ (H2020-SMEINST-2-2016-2017) (Grant agreement n. 783696) is kindly acknowledged.

The authors also thank Dr. Rocco Perniola (CREA) and Mr Giacomo Suglia (Consortium NuVaUT) for the kind collaboration.

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